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URBAN-WASTE

Urban strategies for Waste Management in Tourist Cities

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URBANWASTE Gender Strategy

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Abstract

The overall gender strategy for URBAN-WASTE is to embed gender sensitivity throughout the research process and outputs. This gender mainstreaming approach is supported by the EU and international commitments to gender equality, and in particular, through Horizon2020. URBAN-WASTE encourages and supports moves towards organisational structures in tourism waste management in which men and women from different backgrounds thrive, leading to more economically, environmentally and socially sustainable practices.

From the outset, gender considerations were designed to be integral to URBAN-WASTE's entire approach, and this Gender Strategy identifies how this will be achieved. Fundamental to its strategy is the undertaking to raise gender awareness and expertise amongst all stakeholders.

As well as work programme packages which address gender equality and sensitivity explicitly (WPs 3 and 4), gender informs all other areas of URBAN-WASTE, such as analysis of the urban metabolism, and in the development of ICT strategies. As these areas are currently rather gender-blind, this inclusion will further the state of knowledge in these fields.

All qualitative and quantitative empirical data that is collected will be gender-differentiated, and intersectional, from the design of data collection through to its analysis and dissemination. Likewise, URBAN-WASTE strategies to prevent, minimise and otherwise manage waste will be gender sensitive and will be developed and tested with regard to gender, and other intersectional characteristics.

Mutual learning (ML) throughout the project is gender-sensitised by the first ML event being dedicated to developing gender awareness. This is made available both to identified stakeholders through a tailored workshop, and in a session open to a wider cohort of tourism waste managers. From this, ML participants will be able to share awareness with colleagues and other stakeholders across the project, and by cascading their learning throughout the case study cities. Resources on gender awareness and good practice are made available on-line to URBAN-WASTE participants, by lodging these in an on-line folder. These resources include reports, academic articles, digests, briefings, and guidelines for gender-sensitive research.

The gender auditor is centrally placed within the Management Group and Steering Committee, and is available to provide advice and expertise throughout the life of URBAN-WASTE. The operations of URBAN-WASTE are mindful of gender equality, and also caring roles, and aim that project working practices are gender sensitive and family friendly.

Project outputs will be informed by gender sensitivity in the ways in which they are analysed, written and disseminated.

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List of abbreviations

CE	Consulta Europa
GA	Gender Auditor
WP	Work Package
D	Deliverable
CoP	Communities of Practices
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
EU	The European Union
EC	European Commission
EASME	European Agency for Small and Medium Enterprises
MMLP	Mobilization and Mutual learning Plan

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1. Outline of Strategy

The overall gender strategy for URBAN-WASTE is ultimately to mainstream gender into waste management in tourist cities across Europe. In order to accomplish this, the strategy incorporates the following objectives:

- i) To embed gender considerations transversally, that is across all aspects of the work programme;
- ii) to establish a gender sensitive database¹ by collecting gender differentiated data;
- iii) to facilitate the acquisition of gender awareness and sensitivity by project partners, which can be cascaded through organisations in the partner cities;
- iv) to contribute to the state of the art of knowledge on the role of gender in tourism and waste management;
- v) to adopt a gender sensitive and family friendly way of working within the project.

2. Background to Gender Strategy

a. Justification of strategy

The need for a gender strategy can be found in the EU commitment to gender equality and its adoption of gender mainstreaming. This is now embedded in the requirements of Horizon2020 by which URBAN-WASTE is funded. The UN Beijing Women's conference in 1995 established the principle of 'gender mainstreaming' in which all government policies and practices should, as a matter of course, be evaluated for their impacts on men and women, so that neither group is disproportionately discriminated against. The EU legally incorporated this in 1996, binding all member states to its enactment. According to Walby (2005: 461), although there are "weaknesses in implementation", the EU has "become a transnational actor that is very important for the contemporary development of gender mainstreaming with strengths in promoting the policy in abstract." The Amsterdam Treaty, signed in 1997, formalized fundamental rights and provided mechanisms by which these must be upheld by member states. Where previously it was illegal to discriminate other than on grounds of nationality, the revised Article 13 "enabled the Council to take appropriate action to combat discrimination based on sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation." (European Union 1997). Whereas previous legislation referred to equality in rates of pay between men and women, the new Treaty introduced two additional articles. These included the promotion of equality between men and women (Article 2 amendment), and a new paragraph which was added to Article 3 stating that: "In all the other activities referred to in this Article, the Community shall aim to eliminate inequalities, and to promote equality, between men and women." (European Union 1997). Debates have moved forward since this time to incorporate the full range of

¹ By database, we are referring to the empirical data collected by URBAN-WASTE in the form of surveys, focus groups and interviews.

gender and to consider how gender intersects with other inequalities, sometimes abbreviated to 'Gender+' (Verloo *et al*, 2011).

Gender mainstreaming can be justified on the instrumental grounds that financial performance, efficiency and/or creativity and innovation increases when boards of major companies are gender balanced (McKinsey, 2016). This, however, neglects the gender justice objective, and leads Angela McRobbie (2009) to suggest that gender mainstreaming bolsters neoliberal managerialism by focusing on how decision making can benefit from women's skills and knowledge, rather than on the gender justice of equal opportunities (and outcomes) for women. Further, Grosser and Moon argue that gender mainstreaming benefits the corporate social responsibility agenda, "simultaneously good for both business and wider society" (in Walby 2005, 457). It is therefore important to recognise that the effective implementation of gender mainstreaming should recognise both that women should have equal rights to men (eg to participate in careers and in civic engagement), and that operational benefits accrue to organisations which strive to achieve gender balance in decision making. Mieke Verloo was positive about the aims of gender mainstreaming to prioritize the lives and experiences of individuals, in its potential to lead to better government, to involve women as well as men, in acknowledging the diversity amongst men and women, and to make gender equality issues visible "in the mainstream of society" (1999, 8). However, she was sceptical that sufficient expertise existed amongst planning professionals to challenge prevailing discourses, and to align the necessary interests from those "at the top" and those "down under" in the planning system. The EU (EIGE, 2015) refers to descriptive and substantive equal representation, which recognises that while equal numbers are important to achieve a critical mass which provides a decision making environment in which both women and men have the confidence to make effective interventions that are respectfully received, it is not in itself sufficient. Both Roehr *et al* (2008) and Magnúsdóttir and Kronsell (2015) stress the role of masculinist institutions in determining working practices which can limit the opportunities of women (and men) with caring responsibilities. It is therefore important to not simply recruit gender balanced panels, communities of practice and so on, but also to ensure a diversity of experience of those men and women who are invited. These reports suggest that despite 20 years of gender mainstreaming, it remains poorly understood. The challenge of URBAN-WASTE is to support a move towards organisational structures in which women and men with different backgrounds can thrive, and to contribute to the creation of conditions in which employees can develop the necessary expertise to mainstream gender awareness and sensitivity across the work of their organisations. If this is achieved, then the conditions for more environmentally sustainable policy and behaviour are more likely to be created (Ergas and York, 2012).

b. Gender in the URBAN-WASTE project

The URBAN-WASTE project has, from the outset, been committed to developing both eco-innovative and gender-sensitive waste prevention and management strategies in cities with high levels of tourism. It sees the integration of both strategies as necessary in order to reduce urban waste production and improve municipal waste management.

Gender balance in decision making at all scales, from the individual to the corporate and municipal is well recognized as likely to have an impact on decisions made (EIGE, 2015; European Union, 2016; McKinsey & Co, 2016). Attention to gender in the project will enable a better understanding of how waste related decisions are

made, contribute to more nuanced research and deliver more robust outcomes. URBAN-WASTE will therefore improve the current understanding of how social and economic differences and inequalities (including gender) affect waste production and disposal and can integrate this knowledge in the actual operation of waste management policies. By this it can contribute to developing debates on gender+ (Verloo *et al*, 2011)

URBAN-WASTE has adopted an urban metabolism perspective which it integrates with a socio-economic analysis crucially informed by gender. By involving stakeholders covering the whole waste value chain, the project introduces a circular metabolism approach which sees waste as a resource and at the same time engages stakeholders in the policy-making value chain, creating an innovative engagement model in waste management policies.

A further aspect of the project has been to recognise the likely lack of gender awareness/expertise amongst potential stakeholders, and therefore the need for gender to be an early mutual learning event, as part of the Mobilization and Mutual Learning (MMLP) programme. MMLP has been designed to be participatory, directly involving citizens, NGOs, SMEs, tourists and tourism providers. By introducing gender sensitivity in an early MMLP workshop, participants are able to share what they learn, thereby cascading an awareness of gender, and its importance, through their local organisations. The aim of this is to develop gender sensitive eco-innovative strategies.

In the process of developing waste management strategies, gender will also play a crucial role. Gender issues have been poorly understood and largely neglected in waste management and most other environmental and technical sectors. This is reflected in low proportions of women employed in these sectors and lower still proportions in senior decision making positions (EY, 2016). A number of studies and reports have stated the importance of a gender sensitive perspective. A gender sensitive perspective is particularly valuable concerning waste management and recycling, for a number of reasons. While waste management remains a highly masculinized profession across Europe (IMF, 2016), when women have been involved in decision making at the municipal level, a difference has been noted in how waste has been managed, and how communities have been engaged in waste minimization. Conversely, at the domestic scale, women are more likely than men to undertake the majority of waste management practices and decisions and yet women are not adequately consulted in the formulation of local waste management strategies, which compromises their effectiveness. These are the conclusions of research for the EU, which explored the existence of and potential for gender mainstreaming municipal waste management in Ireland, Portugal and the UK. (Buckingham, Reeves and Batchelor, 2005)

The URBAN-WASTE research will contribute to currently limited research on gender nuanced patterns in waste production (individuals and businesses) and management (industry and policy making). The knowledge acquired will be disseminated to raise awareness and to build capacities among business and policy makers, and will support the design of gender-sensitive urban strategies which use gender difference and gender expertise to increase their effectiveness. Based on this, URBAN-WASTE will put in place a series of activities for gender mainstreaming in the waste strategies it designs.

While gender is an aspect which traverses the whole URBAN-WASTE programme, facilitated by the gender auditor (GA) who sits on the Management Board, there are specific work programmes in which work on gender is concentrated, as illustrated in italics in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Gender Sensitivity in the Work Programme

Work Programme Requirement	Project Objectives	Activities in the WP	Deliverables involved
“Development of innovative and gender-sensitive strategies for waste prevention and management in urban and peri-urban areas”	Development of innovative strategies for waste prevention and management in urban and peri-urban tourist areas - Test and evaluate the strategies in 11 pilot cities representing 10 EU countries	WP3 – Gender issues analysis WP4 – Design of the strategies WP6 – Implementation of the strategies	D3.5, D3.6 D4.1 D6.3, D6.2
“Proposals should highlight how urban patterns, drivers, consumer behaviour, lifestyle, culture, architecture and socio-economic issues can influence the metabolism of cities”	- Urban metabolic analysis in the 11 cities - Socio-economic analysis in the 11 cities	WP2 – Status quo assessment WP3 – Behavioural and situation analysis WP5 – Mobile application to collect data on tourist lifestyles and behaviours	D2.3, D2.5, D2.7 D3.2, D3.3 D5.1
“Proposals should highlight the possible benefits to be derived from eco-system services and green infrastructure” and their gender-sensitive applications	- Estimation of benefits for tourism from eco-system services - Analysis on gender differences on consumption and waste production patterns - Development of gender sensitive strategies - Awareness raising activities among tourists, business operators on the benefits and on the impact of tourism,	WP2 – Estimation of impact of waste on ecosystem services and of benefits for tourism from eco system services WP3 – Focus groups on gender; Awareness raising measures among stakeholders involved in the MMLAP WP4- Gender auditing of waste prevention and management strategies WP8- Dissemination activities	D2.6 D3.5, D3.6 D4.1 D8.3, D8.4

	waste production on them		
Proposals should involve active engagement of local authorities, citizens and other stakeholders using innovative concepts such as mobilization and mutual learning	Development and implementation of 11 Mobilization and Mutual Learning Action Plans	WP3- Development of a gender-sensitive MMLAP and of Communities of Practices Involvement in the implementation; Organization of mutual learning events and staff exchanges for policy makers.	D3.4, D3.7 D3.8

3. Transversal embedding of gender considerations

a. Gender in the ‘urban metabolism’

Gender has not been a consideration in studies of ‘urban metabolism’ and ‘urban metabolic flows’. At best, gender is currently included as an additional rather than an integrated aspect of understanding urban metabolism, and at worst is not considered to be at all relevant. Centralising a gender analysis in URBANWASTE represents an innovative departure for ecosystem services and will contribute to more robust conclusions and policy recommendations.

b. Gender in ICT

ICT tools are being developed under WP5. It is established that ICT has a strongly gendered dimension and that men and women tend to use ICT in different ways, and to different extents (EIGE, 2016). This will be reflected in the design of technological and digital solutions to be implemented individually or in conjunction with other measures. Three main tools will be developed:

1. An interactive mobile application (WasteApp), based on a gamification model in which the user (tourist) is rewarded to acknowledge her or his good practice.
2. Interactive maps showing the location of the ‘waste-free’ services, high performing bars/restaurants/hotels and other tourist establishments. The map will be useful for tourists to identify relevant services and tourist providers, and as a promotion tool for tourist businesses.
3. A food waste tracking device for food services will give real time feedback of wasted quantities to kitchen staff, but also can collect detailed waste data for evaluation.

All three tools will be designed, prototyped and developed with due regard for gender differences.

4. Establishing a gender sensitive database

a. Researching gender differences in waste and tourism

WP3 will aim at understanding (through desk research, surveys, interviews and focus groups) how gender determines consumers' and policy makers' attitudes towards resources so that changes to policy and practice can engage fully, fairly and effectively with both men and women at all stages of the waste production and management cycle. Gender differences in consumption, use of resources and waste production and management will be investigated by means of questionnaires, interviews and focus groups, while a gender audit will be performed in the pilot cities to assess the degree of awareness and the gender balance in the decision-making processes behind urban waste planning. Three gender-sensitive surveys are designed for waste managers, tourist workers and tourists in each of the 11 partner cities to enable URBAN-WASTE to understand professional and personal attitudes and behaviour towards waste management. The results of this inform the three focus groups for waste managers, tourism workers and tourists to be run in each city.

The gender mainstreaming carried out during the analysis of the URBAN-WASTE strategies, will allow the creation of innovative gender sensitive waste management strategies, that could be replicated in other tourist and non-tourist cities in the EU. We can expect that this will lead to better ecosystem service management.

b. Intersectionality

As intersectionality is an important aspect of gender, the research will ensure that both men and women from a range of socio-economic and cultural groups, and different parental status, are encouraged to participate, as relevant for each area.

c. Use of the data in the design of waste prevention and management measures

In WP4, the outcomes of the urban metabolism analysis and the results of the gender-sensitive participatory process will be adapted and integrated for the development of eco-innovative, inclusive and gender-sensitive waste prevention and management (collection and recycling) strategies. These strategies will address three main target groups: citizens and tourists, business operators and policy-makers. The adaptation and adjustment phase

of the strategies will also consider the different types of tourism characterizing the cities (recreation, business, nature, religious), since they do not necessarily entail the same types of services and activities, and thus the same behaviours regarding waste generation and management. The measures to be included in the strategies will be the result of a participatory approach to encourage bottom-up innovative ideas. The inclusion of the gender perspective will be ensured in several rounds: at the beginning of the design phase of the measures, before their validation and in their evaluation.

5. Facilitating the acquisition of gender awareness and gender sensitivity

a. Gendering stakeholder engagement and mutual learning

The first (held in December 2016) mutual learning event (MMLP) is aimed to sensitise project partners to gender issues and enable sharing of existing good practice between partner organisations. This has been designed to facilitate the smooth collection of gender sensitive data through the project, and to give partners the confidence to cascade knowledge and consideration of gender awareness through their organisations and communities of practice. This subsequent stage is expected to encompass several initiatives and communication channels, to involve the stakeholders along the whole “policy-making” value chain. It is envisaged that this understanding will gender-sensitise each of the eleven city implementation plans, which will develop local indicators in a participatory way to monitor the effectiveness of gender inclusiveness.

b. Gender supporting activity

Resources on gender awareness and good practice are made available on-line to URBAN-WASTE participants, including briefings, guidelines for gender-sensitive research. In this way, project participants, as well as the GA, can share their own resources and good practice. In addition to the training for gender mainstreaming provided early in the MMLP, the gender auditor will provide support to project partners for local gender budgeting, and for empowerment training to local community and neighbourhood groups on gender equality and women's rights. It will also be an intrinsic part of inviting and enabling descriptively and substantively gender balanced representation in CoPs.

6. Contributing to the state of the art of knowledge on the role of gender in tourism and waste management

The gender auditor will prepare one article on the gender aspects of the URBAN-WASTE project, for publication in an international journal which is accessible and useful for professional waste management practitioners. In addition she will contribute gender analyses to the project report, and to other articles analyzing the project's activities and achievements.

The developing state of the art regarding gender in waste management in tourist areas will be furthered through conference presentations and professional meetings.

7. Working in a gender sensitive way

a. Gender balanced teams

The project seeks to recruit a balance of women and men onto the project, from a range of ages, and social-economic backgrounds, as researchers and as stakeholders. The gender balance of stakeholders has been considered at every stage, and this has informed the appointment of participants in the project's different activity groups and management bodies.

b. Gender sensitive working practices

URBAN-WASTE endeavours to work in a way which respects participants' family life and caring responsibilities by arranging face-to-face meetings which do not require weekend travel, and arranging virtual meetings within the core working hours of 9-5 shared across participating country time zones. Particular attention is paid to the use of technology which minimizes the need for travel.

URBAN-WASTE is committed to working in a mutually respectful environment in which all participants' views are solicited, heard and equally respected.

8. Timeline of gender sensitive activities

Table 2: Timeline of gender-sensitive activities

Activity	June -Dec 2016	Jan-June 2017	July -Dec 2017	Jan-June 2018	July -Dec 2017	Jan-June 2019
Resources	Gender briefing produced and circulated; Guide to running gender sensitive focus groups produced and disseminated.					
Research	Contributed gender sensitivity questions to survey	Gender sensitive focus group briefing guides produced and used				
		Survey to participating waste management organisations to generate gender sensitive database				
		Interviews with women working in waste management	Interviews with women working in waste management	Interviews with women working in waste management	Interviews with women working in waste management	
Mutual Learning	Gender Awareness ML workshop designed and delivered	Gender supporting activities	Gender supporting activities	Gender supporting activities	Gender supporting activities	

Gender Mainstreaming		Gender supporting activities (eg app development)	Gender supporting activities (eg in waste strategy development)	Gender supporting activities	Gender supporting activities	<p data-bbox="635 275 1374 327">This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 690452</p>
Publications/ dissemination		Gender contribution to article on social drivers for tourists' waste management behaviour.				Article on gender in waste management in tourist areas; Gender contributions to report and other articles; gender component in final conference

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